

A REVIEW ON HETUS OF KASA ROGA IN MODERN-DAY PERSPECTIVE

¹*Dr. Ibtisam Mehzebin and ²Dr. Hemen Kalita

¹PG Scholar, Department of Roga Nidan, Govt. Ayurvedic College and Hospital, Jalukbari, Guwahati-14.

²Associate Professor, Department of Roga Nidan, Govt. Ayurvedic College & Hospital, Jalukbari, Guwahati-14.

Article Received on 28 Nov. 2025,
Article Revised on 18 Dec. 2025,
Article Published on 01 Jan. 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18092563>

*Corresponding Author

Dr. Ibtisam Mehzebin

PG Scholar, Department of Roga Nidan, Govt. Ayurvedic College and Hospital, Jalukbari, Guwahati-14.

How to cite this Article: 1*Dr. Ibtisam Mehzebin and 2Dr. Hemen Kalita. (2026). A REVIEW ON HETUS OF KASA ROGA IN MODERN-DAY PERSPECTIVE. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 15(1), 204–210.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Kasa Roga, a common disorder of the *Pranavaha Srotas*, is described in Ayurveda as a condition that may arise as a *Swatantra Vyadhi* (independent disease), a *Lakshana* (symptom) or an *Upadrava* (complication). In Ayurveda Kasa roga is classified into into five types based on the predominance of Dosha and nature of obstruction. If neglected, Kasa may progress to a poor prognostic stage. Modern medicine defines cough as a protective reflex aiding in airway clearance, with significant prevalence across both rural and urban populations. Ayurveda identifies several etiological factors (*hetus*) for Kasa, including Raja (dust), Dhooma (smoke), Ruksha Anna (dry foods), Snigdha Anna (unctuous foods) and Abhishyandi Ahara (channel-blocking foods). When interpreted in a modern context, these correlate with environmental dust exposure, air pollution, vehicular emissions, dry food habits, excessive oily food intake and

consumption of heavy, Kapha-increasing foods. These factors collectively contribute to airway irritation, phlegm formation and increased susceptibility to respiratory disorders. Understanding the correlation between classical Ayurvedic etiological factors and their modern equivalents is essential for accurate diagnosis of Kasa. This alignment helps practitioners apply classical principles effectively within contemporary clinical settings.

KEYWORDS: Kasa roga, Pranavaha srotas, Hetu, Raja, dhooma.

INTRODUCTION

Kasa Roga is one of the most common ailments afflicting the *Pranavaha Srotas*.^[1] It may develop as a *Swatantra Vyadhi*^[2] (independent disease) or as a *Lakshana* (symptom) associated with other diseases. It may also occur as an *Upadrava* (complication) of various conditions. When it manifests as a *Swatantra Vyadhi*, it is classified into five types as described in classical Ayurvedic texts. The characteristic sound and pain differ among the five types of *Kasa Roga* depending on the predominant *dosha* and the nature of obstruction involved. If neglected, *Kasa Roga* may progress to a condition with poor prognosis.

Cough, in modern medicine, is defined as a reflex act of forceful expiration against a closed glottis, which helps in clearing the airways, including foreign bodies.^[3] The prevalence of cough has been reported as 2.4–5.6% in rural areas and 1.7–5.4% in urban areas.^[4]

Although Ayurveda clearly described the etiological *hetus* of *Kasa roga* such as *Raja* (dust), *Dhooma* (smoke), *Ruksha anna* (dry food items), *Snigdha anna* (Unctous food) and *Abhishyandi ahara* (channel blocking foods) but their practical interpretation in modern lifestyle still remains unexplored. Therefore, a study to explore the *hetus* of *Kasa roga* in modern day perspective is the need of the hour,

MATERIALS AND METHOD

□ **Study Design:** Literary review and conceptual analysis based on classical Ayurvedic texts, commentaries and contemporary research.

□ Sources

- *Bṛihatrayee*'s and *Laghutrayee*'s
- Various journals & articles

□ METHODOLOGY

- Compilation and categorization of all *nidana*'s of *Kasa*
- Constructing a correlation model between Ayurvedic etiological concepts and contemporary respiratory pathology.

DISCUSSION

Kasa is described as a *Praṇavaha srotas gata vikara* (disorder of the respiratory system), primarily characterized by repeated and forceful expulsion of *vata* through the mouth, often accompanied by sound and discomfort. As per Charaka, the vitiation of *doṣhas*, particularly *Vata* is the cause of *Kasa*, which involves the irritation and blockage of respiratory passages. According to Classics, *Raja-dhooma sevana* (inhalation of dust and smoke), *Dooṣhita vayu sevana* (exposure to polluted air or strong winds), *Abhiṣhyandi ahara* (heavy, kapha-increasing foods), *Ruksha* and *Snigdha anna* are some of the *hetus*^[6] of *Kasa roga*. On the other hand, these factors can be understood in the context of present time as follows:

In Ayurveda, *Raja* refers to dust, which is considered an important environmental irritant contributing to various respiratory conditions. In the context of modern lifestyle, this can be correlated with frequent dust exposure during daily commuting in buses, cars, and two-wheelers as well as exposure encountered during indoor and outdoor activities.^[7] Increased urbanization, ongoing construction work, poor air quality and inadequate ventilation further aggravate *Raja*-related exposure. Such continuous contact with dust may lead to irritation of the respiratory tract, flaring up of allergic manifestations and increased susceptibility to disorders like *Kasa*. Hence, *Raja* can be considered a significant contemporary risk factor that parallels the classical understanding of environmental *Nidanas*.

In Ayurveda, *Dhooma* refers to smoke, which is recognized as an important environmental irritant capable of aggravating the respiratory system. In modern era, exposure to smoke occurs through vehicle emissions, industrial pollution, burning of waste, cooking smoke, indoor incense^[8] or camphor and tobacco smoke. Such chronic or repeated exposure can irritate the airways, reduce lung function and increase the risk of respiratory disorders like *Kasa*, *Shwasa* and allergic conditions. Thus, *Dhooma* remains a significant *hetu* even today, paralleling contemporary environmental pollutants impacting respiratory health.

According to Ayurveda, *Ruksha Dravya*'s^[9] are those which are dry, light, rough, sharply acting, hot, stable, non-slimy and primarily hard. *Vayu mahabhuta* is predominant in *ruksha dravyas*. Substances having *katu*, *tikta* and *kashaya rasa*'s are *ruksha* in nature.^[10] The *karma*^[11] (action) of *ruksha dravya*'s are those that causes dryness, roughness and coarseness. In the modern diet, frequent consumption of items like Chips, bhujia, papad^[12], crackers, toasters, baked foods, crackers, toasted foods and insufficiently oiled or moist meals can increase dryness in the body. This dryness may lead to irritation, frequent coughing and can

worsen conditions like *Kasa*. Thus, *Ruksha Anna* continues to be an important dietary contributor to *Vata*-dominant respiratory conditions in current lifestyles.

According to Ayurveda, *Snigdha Anna*^[13] refers to foods that are oily, moist, and nourishing. *Snigdha dravya*'s are those which possess qualities like- liquid, minute (subtle), flowing (unstable), unctuous, slimy, heavy, cold, sluggish and soft. *Snigdha guna* is found in madhura (sweet), *amla* (sour) and *lavana* (salty) *dravya*'s.^[14] The *Karma*^[15] (actions) of *snigdha dravya*'s are those which moisturizes and smoothens causes unctious, fluidity and ooze. These foods help balance *Vata* by providing lubrication to body tissues, including the respiratory tract. In modern diets, items prepared with adequate ghee or healthy oils can prevent dryness of the throat and airways, reducing irritation and coughing. However, excessive intake of heavy, oily foods may increase *Kapha* leading to congestion and worsening of cough in some individuals. Therefore, *Snigdha Anna* plays an important role in maintaining proper balance and supporting respiratory health.

Abhishyandi Ahara refers to foods that are heavy, sticky and tend to block the body's channels (*srotas*). In modern diet patterns, items like curd, cheese, deep-fried foods, bakery products, and excessively oily dishes can increase *Kapha* and create a feeling of heaviness and congestion. Such foods may obstruct the respiratory passages, worsen phlegm formation, and aggravate conditions like cough, cold and *Kasa*. Therefore, *Abhishyandi* foods are an important dietary factor that can trigger or worsen respiratory problems when taken in excess.

CONCLUSION

From the study the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. *Raja* and *Dhooma* are the modern-day pollutants. *Raja* can be identified as frequent dust exposure during daily commuting in buses, cars, and two-wheelers as well as exposure encountered during indoor and outdoor activities. Increased urbanization, ongoing construction work, poor air quality and inadequate ventilation further aggravate *Raja*-related exposure. On the other hand, *Dhooma* can be identified as exposure to smoke occurs through vehicle emissions, industrial pollution, burning of waste, cooking smoke, indoor incense or camphor and tobacco smoke. Continuous exposure to dust and smoke aggravates *doshas* and it contributes to the development and worsening of respiratory disorders such as *Kasa*.

2. *Ruksha Anna* can be identified as Chips, bhujia, papad¹², toaster, crackers, baked foods, crackers, toasted foods and insufficiently oiled or moist meals, making individuals more vulnerable to cough and exacerbating conditions like *Kasa* in present-day lifestyles.
3. *Snigdha Anna* supports respiratory health by reducing dryness. It can be identified as the items prepared by oil, ghee or butter but excessive intake may increase *Kapha* and congestion, indicating the need for balanced consumption to prevent aggravation of *Kasa*.
4. *Abhishyandi Ahara* can be identified as curd, cheese, etc which leads to *Kapha* accumulation and *srotas* obstruction, leading to worsening of cough, phlegm and *Kasa* when consumed in excess.

REFERENCES

1. Deeza CR, Satya Priya T, Venkat Shivudu K, Ram Reddy GP. Clinical evaluation of Hareetakyadi gutika on Kaphaja Kasa. International journal of Ayurvedic Medicine, 2013; 4(4): 394-404.
2. Dr. Bhavika Chaudhari, Dr. Sachin Deva, Dr. Neha Agnihotri. A clinical evaluation of Kaphaja Kasa (Chronic or Recurrent mucopurulent bronchitis)- A case study doi: 10.17051/ilkonline.2021.05.580.
3. Alagappan R, Manual of Practical Medicine, Published by- Jaypee brothers medical publishers (p) ltd, 4th edition 2011, Chapter 4, Respiratory system, Page no. 201.
4. P.A Mahesh, B.S Jayaraj, A.K Prabhakar, S.K Chaya, R. Vijayasimha Prevalence of Chronic Cough, Chronic Phlegm & associated factors in Mysore, Karnataka, India. Indian J Med Res-2011 July; 134(1): 91-100.
5. Dr. Bhavika Chaudhari, Dr. Sachin Deva, Dr. Neha Agnihotri. A clinical evaluation of Kaphaja Kasa (Chronic or Recurrent mucopurulent bronchitis)- A case study doi: 10.17051/ilkonline.2021.05.580.
6. Pt. Shastri Pandey Kashinath & Dr. Chaturvedi Gorakhnath, Vol 2, Charaka Samhita of Agnivesha by Vidyotini commentary, Published by- Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, Edition 2020, Reprint- 2021, Chapter 18, Kasa chikitsa adhyay, Verse no. 10,14,17,20,24, Page no. 481-483.
7. Dr. Deka Majani, Dr. Kalita Hemen, An Etiopathological Study of Childhood Asthma in Ayurveda with special reference to Shwasa Roga, Page no. 69.
8. Dr. Deka Majani, Dr. Kalita Hemen, An Etiopathological Study of Childhood Asthma in Ayurveda with special reference to Shwasa Roga, Page no.70

9. Pt. Shastri Pandey Kashinath & Dr. Chaturvedi Gorakhnath, Charaka Samhita of Agnivesha by Vidyotini commentary, Vol 1, Published by- Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, Edition 2019, Reprint- 2020, Chapter 22, Langhanabrahmaniya adhyay, Verse no. 14, Page no. 371.
10. Pt. Shastri Pandey Kashinath & Dr. Chaturvedi Gorakhnath, Charaka Samhita of Agnivesha by Vidyotini commentary, Vol 1, Published by- Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, Edition 2019, Reprint- 2020, Chapter 26, Atreyabhadrakapyeeya adhyay, Verse no. 53, Page no. 443.
11. Pt. Shastri Pandey Kashinath & Dr. Chaturvedi Gorakhnath, Charaka Samhita of Agnivesha by Vidyotini commentary, Vol 1, Published by- Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, Edition 2019, Reprint- 2020, Chapter 22, Langhanabrahmaniya adhyay, Verse no. 10, Page no. 370.
12. Dr. Deka Majani, Dr. Kalita Hemen, An Etiopathological Study of Childhood Asthma in Ayurveda with special reference to Shwasa Roga, Page no. 67.
13. Pt. Shastri Pandey Kashinath & Dr. Chaturvedi Gorakhnath, Charaka Samhita of Agnivesha by Vidyotini commentary, Vol 1, Published by- Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, Edition 2019, Reprint- 2020, Chapter 22, Langhanabrahmaniya adhyay, Verse no. 15, Page no. 371.
14. Pt. Shastri Pandey Kashinath & Dr. Chaturvedi Gorakhnath, Charaka Samhita of Agnivesha by Vidyotini commentary, Vol 1, Published by- Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, Edition 2019, Reprint- 2020, Chapter 26, Atreyabhadrakapyeeya adhyay, Verse no. 54, Page no. 443.
15. Pt. Shastri Pandey Kashinath & Dr. Chaturvedi Gorakhnath, Charaka Samhita of Agnivesha by Vidyotini commentary, Vol 1, Published by- Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, Edition 2019, Reprint- 2020, Chapter 22, Langhanabrahmaniya adhyay, Verse no. 10, Page no. 370.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Pt. Shastri Pandey Kashinath & Dr. Chaturvedi Gorakhnath, Vol 1, Charaka Samhita of Agnivesha by Vidyotini commentary, Published by- Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, Edition 2020, Reprint- 2021.
2. Pt. Shastri Pandey Kashinath & Dr. Chaturvedi Gorakhnath, Charaka Samhita of Agnivesha by Vidyotini commentary, Vol 2, Published by- Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, Edition- 2019, Reprint-2020.

3. Alagappan R, Manual of Practical Medicine, Published by - Jaypee brothers medical publishers (p) ltd, 4th edition 2011.
4. Dr. Majani Deka and Dr. Hemen Kalita, An Etiopathological Study of Childhood Asthma in Ayurveda with special reference to Shwasa Roga, 2024.